

ECOEPIDEMIOLOGY OF AVIAN INFLUENZA AND OTHER DISEASES IN DALMATIAN PELICANS

SUMMARY BRIEF

Compiled by
Olga Alexandrou
Giorgos Catsadorakis
Ursula Höfle

This Summary Brief is based on the findings of research on the “Ecoepidemiology¹ of avian influenza and other diseases in Dalmatian pelicans”. The brief summarises the full research report, aiming to make its important findings accessible to a wide range of readers. The research was carried out through a collaboration between the Society for the Protection of Prespa (SPP), a Greek non-profit, non-governmental organization working since 1991 to protect the globally important Prespa lakes, home to the largest Dalmatian pelican colony on Earth, and the University of Castilla-La Mancha / IREC-CSIC in Spain, an institute investigating infectious diseases in free-living wild birds. Both parties made substantial contributions to the conception and design of the study. Professor Ursula Höfle, of the University of Castilla-La Mancha, had the leading role in the design of the research, the analyses and the writing of the final research report. The SPP team carried out the sampling, and Dr Olga Alexandrou and Dr Giorgos Catsadorakis reviewed and commented on several drafts of the research report.

¹ Ecoepidemiology is the study of how a disease spreads in an animal population and the impact it has on this population related to the ecology of the animal species but also the agent (pathogen) that causes the disease.

5

INTRODUCTION

8

THE NEED FOR RESEARCH

14

SAMPLING

17

LABORATORY WORK

18

RESULTS

28

WHAT HAVE WE LEARNED FROM ALL THIS?

INTRODUCTION

In spring 2022, Dalmatian pelican *Pelecanus crispus* (hereafter DP) populations in SE Europe were severely affected by an outbreak of highly pathogenic avian influenza (hereafter HPAI) virus. Over 40% of the SE European breeding population was lost, corresponding to approximately 10% of the global population of the species. Almost 2,300 DPs died in Greece, and another 190 DP deaths were recorded in Albania, Montenegro and Romania.

The largest breeding colony of the species on Earth, at Lesser (Mikri) Prespa Lake in NW Greece, suffered major losses. From February to April 2022, the virus (H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b) killed almost 1,800 adult DPs in Prespa, about 60% of the colony. This outbreak was the worst ecological disaster ever suffered by the country's wildlife. Yet, not all breeding colonies in Greece were equally affected. The two western, coastal colonies in the Amvrakikos wetlands and Messolonghi lagoons were not affected at all, while the four eastern colonies at Lesser Prespa Lake, Lake Kerkini, Lake Cheimaditida and Karla Reservoir lost varying numbers of birds, with the Prespa colony hit hardest.

In the rest of the world, gregarious species were especially affected, particularly those that nest colonially. Across Europe, northern gannets *Morus bassanus*, sandwich terns *Thalasseus sandvicensis*, barnacle geese *Branta leucopsis* and great skuas *Stercorarius skua* suffered exceptionally high losses. Thousands of common cranes *Grus grus* died in Israel, and high numbers of Peruvian pelicans *Pelecanus thagus* were wiped out in South America. This susceptibility, or vulnerability, is likely correlated with the social behaviour of many waterbird and seabird species, as large groupings of individuals give the virus ample opportunity to spread rapidly.

However, great white pelicans *Pelecanus onocrotalus* (hereafter GWP) were not affected by the outbreak, despite sharing breeding grounds and habitat with DPs at the Lesser Prespa colony and also being a colonial species. Few GWP deaths were recorded at the Kerkini and Karla colonies, though deaths at Karla also included nestlings of both species. None of the other affected colonies reported deaths of nestlings of either species, as no colony other than Karla had hatched chicks at the onset of the outbreak. The much lower impact of the outbreak on GWPs leads to the hypothesis that DPs are more susceptible to the avian influenza (hereafter AI) virus than their fellow species.

Experts around the globe agree that there is no effective way to protect wild birds by treating this epizootic disease. They recommend the immediate removal of dead birds, if possible, to reduce the viral load and limit the spread of the disease and its catastrophic effects. At Lesser Prespa Lake, strenuous efforts in the marshes and shallow open-water wetlands resulted in the removal of 1,420 deceased DPs from the lake. These birds weighed approximately 15 tons and had to be removed using small boats.

THE DALMATIAN PELICAN

The Dalmatian pelican (DP) is an emblematic Palearctic bird species ranging from eastern Europe to China. DPs live mainly in inland freshwater wetlands, rivers, lakes, deltas and estuaries, where they feed almost exclusively on fish. The SE European population of DPs consists of short-distance migrant populations from Greece, Albania, Montenegro, Bulgaria, Romania, Ukraine and Turkey. In Greece, the birds belonging to the aforementioned eastern colonies winter close to their breeding grounds and usually migrate to wetlands in north/northeastern Greece and western Turkey. Lesser Prespa Lake in Greece hosts the largest breeding colony of DPs in the world, where they breed side-by-side with the great white pelican (GWP), which shows similar feeding behaviour and habitat preferences. However, GWPs are long-distance migrants that fly through many important stopover sites on their southward migration to African wetlands along the Rift Valley to winter in eastern Africa.

The transmission cycle of avian influenza

AVIAN INFLUENZA

Most strains of avian influenza (AI) are not highly pathogenic (highly pathogenic strains cause high rates of death when birds are infected) and cause few signs of disease in infected wild birds. Highly pathogenic avian influenza is an emerging and unexpected threat to wildlife and has implications for ecological processes, ecosystem services and the conservation of threatened species. Its origin has been tracked back to poultry farms, as wild birds are NOT the natural reservoirs of highly pathogenic strains. Intensive poultry production boosts the aggressiveness of the virus, as well as the transmission of highly pathogenic strains.

HOW is the disease spread?

Infected birds can shed AI viruses in their saliva, faeces and secretions from the nasal cavity and uropygial gland at the base of the tail feathers. Susceptible birds become infected when they come into contact with the virus shed by infected birds. They also can become infected through contact with surfaces that are contaminated with viruses from infected birds as the AI virus can, at low temperatures and in high humidity, persist for prolonged periods in faeces.

THE NEED FOR RESEARCH

The heavy losses at the Lesser Prespa colony were alarming for the conservation of the species and raised several questions.

EXPOSURE

How and where did these DPs become infected?

Two basic scenarios were considered:

- The DPs acquired the AI virus at their wintering grounds or staging points on the way. They arrived at their Prespa breeding grounds already infected. A few days later they got sick and died.
- The DPs arrived in good health and were contaminated at their Prespa breeding grounds. The AI virus was circulating in other waterbird species that use the same habitats at Prespa. These other species were asymptomatic, showing no signs of the disease, and spread the virus through their secretions.

THE HEALTH STATUS OF PELICAN POPULATIONS IN GREECE

What are the underlying reasons for the susceptibility of DPs to the AI virus?

Can the difference in susceptibility between the two pelican species be explained?

How are the different severities of impact between different DP colonies explained?

Several factors may have contributed to the susceptibility of DPs:

- **Behaviour:** At their breeding and roosting sites, the birds are densely grouped, which may facilitate the spread of the AI virus. Intense interaction between them, such as pecking during the mating season, the exchange of saliva and nasal secretions or the collection of possibly contaminated nest-building material, such as reed stems, may also facilitate the spread of the virus. The early start to the breeding cycle may play a role, as DPs start breeding in winter when temperatures are low, and the virus is more likely to persist and be transmitted more successfully.
- **Genetics:** Genetic diversity strengthens the ability of populations to resist diseases. Low genetic diversity could greatly increase the percentage of infected individuals in a population and/or contribute to lower resistance.
- **Other viruses or bacteria:** Other diseases may be affecting DPs at the same time as the AI virus, suppressing their immune system.
- **Environmental factors:** The persistence of the AI virus in aquatic environments and at low temperatures may be a particularly important factor for the Lesser Prespa colony, which lies at an altitude of 850m, with temperatures during the onset of the DP breeding period being often close to 0°C. Likewise, the fact that DPs share their breeding and especially roosting sites with other waterbird species may also be an important factor.

A mixed breeding colony of Dalmatian and great white pelicans at Lesser Prespa Lake.

In July 2022, immediately after the disastrous outbreak at Prespa, research was launched to seek answers to the above questions and investigate the exposure of DPs and GWPs to the AI virus, as well as to comparatively study the dynamics of avian pathogens, both between DP colonies and between DPs and GWPs. The main aim was to shed light on the possible culprit factors that are responsible for DP susceptibility to the AI virus. At the same time, a global DP genetic study was also launched, the outcomes of which could potentially reveal crucial factors, however this *Summary Brief* refers solely to the former study.

THE SPP'S PELICAN CONSERVATION EFFORTS

Active conservation efforts for pelicans in Greece and other SE European countries started in the early 1980s. These included research, monitoring and hands-on measures, such as the designation of protected areas, safeguarding nesting sites from disturbance and the construction of artificial nesting structures. Aided by favourable changes in several environmental and socio-cultural factors, this work in Greece by the SPP and the Hellenic Ornithological Society resulted in an impressive increase of DP numbers from a few hundred to over 2,300 breeding pairs in the early 2020s.

Lesser Prespa Lake
affected colony

Cheimaditida Lake
affected colony

Amvrakikos Wetlands
unaffected colony

Messolonghi Lagoons
unaffected colony

Kerkini Lake
affected colony

Karla Reservoir
affected colony

Dalmatian pelicans in Europe form two almost distinct population groups, the western and the eastern one. Little interaction exists between the two groups, however, within the group, there is ample interaction. In Greece, the eastern population group consists of the four colonies that were all affected during the 2022 outbreak, whereas the two western colonies were not affected at all.

SAMPLING

A sampling protocol was designed, which primarily focused on collecting samples from live birds, with environmental samples also collected, but to a smaller extent.

LIVE BIRD SAMPLES

The live bird samples collected included blood samples, choanal and cloacal swabs, as well as feather samples. Choanal swabs were taken from the choanal cleft, a small split on the roof of the middle part of the upper mandible which opens into the nasal cavity. Cloacal swabs were taken from the cloaca, the bird's single opening for its urinary, intestinal and reproductive tracts.

Samples were taken from:

1. DP and GWP nestlings at the Lesser Prespa colony in the 2022 breeding season.
2. DP and GWP nestlings in all but one of the Greek pelican colonies in the 2023 breeding season.
3. DP adults and immatures before the onset of the 2023 breeding season.
4. DP adults and immatures before the onset of the 2024 breeding season.

RESEARCH CHALLENGES

Unfortunately, sampling of the DPs that died from highly pathogenic avian influenza virus was not allowed during the 2022 outbreak, other than that carried out by the veterinary authorities. If such samples had been available, they would allow the comparison of findings from dead, infected birds and live birds. In other words, there may have been apparent differences in the intestinal and respiratory microbiota that could explain the susceptibility of DPs to the virus. Furthermore, such material could have provided a more detailed view of the origin and development of the disease and its transmission routes. The absence of such samples has been a key weakness of this research.

A photograph showing several researchers in white protective suits, masks, and gloves working in a field. They are focused on sampling nestlings. One researcher in the foreground is writing on a clipboard. The background shows tall grass and other researchers in similar attire.

Sampling nestlings at the Lesser Prespa colony in July 2022, just after the catastrophic avian influenza outbreak.

ENVIRONMENTAL SAMPLES

Two different types of environmental samples were proactively collected in late 2022, before the onset of 2023 breeding season, and were tested for the AI virus:

1. Faeces of DPs and other waterbirds using the same areas, such as great cormorants, greylag geese and mute swans, were collected at Lesser Prespa and at nearby Lake Kastoria, which is heavily used by pelicans, as a feeding, resting and staging site.
2. Nesting material mixed with faeces, feathers and plant debris from Lesser Prespa DP nests used in 2022 breeding season.

Environmental samples were tested in order to examine the hypothesis that other waterfowl species using the sites of the outbreak were acting as a source for the virus, as well as the potential persistence of the AI virus in nesting material or faeces at nesting sites. Regarding waterfowl, there is ample evidence of birds such as mallards *Anas platyrhynchos* and teals *Anas crecca* (both are duck species) showing AI infection in the absence of clinical signs.

LABORATORY WORK

All the environmental and live bird samples were treated in order to concentrate and isolate the genetic material they contained, which was then specifically tested for the AI virus. Cloacal and choanal swab samples from adult and nestling pelicans were also used in bacterial cultures using different media, to screen for the diversity of bacterial species present in the upper respiratory tract in both DPs and GWPs, as well as the detection of potential bacterial pathogens in the cloaca. Finally, serum samples were analysed for the presence of antibodies against the AI virus and the West Nile virus.

RESULTS

AVIAN INFLUENZA VIRUSES

The AI virus was not detected in any of the DP and GWP nestlings at Lesser Prespa in 2022, nor at any colony in 2023. In the case of the Prespa DP nestlings in 2022, it should be noted that they were the offspring of the surviving or unaffected breeders. As infection with H5N1 meant a quick death for most DPs, its absence in evidently healthy birds was rather to be expected. Furthermore, the AI virus was not detected in adult DPs trapped for radio telemetry in early 2023 and 2024.

Antibodies for AI virus subtypes other than H5 were detected in 10% of the DP nestlings that hatched after the 2022 outbreak at the Prespa colony, but in none of the GWP nestlings. AI virus antibodies can be transferred from females to their chicks through the egg yolk. No data exist on the duration of antibody levels in pelicans, but experimental and field data for gulls suggest a short duration for maternal antibodies, lasting for two to three weeks after hatching. Given that these nestlings were sampled at an age of more than six weeks, the antibodies that were found are likely to reflect environmental exposure and not maternal antibodies. Environmental exposure could result from proximity to infected DPs or GWPs, or other species that may visit nesting islands, or contaminated water or soil close to the nest. Various AI subtypes

can coexist and circulate in wild birds and the antibodies found in the DP nestlings likely reflect exposure to a non-pathogenic (non-disease causing) AI virus. Depending on the subtype antibodies generated from such exposure could confer some immunity against H5.

No HPAI virus antibodies were detected in any nestlings at any colony in the 2023 breeding season. This probably means that HPAI virus did not circulate in pelican colonies in 2023, which would be consistent with the absence of mass deaths observed in that year.

An adult Dalmatian pelican in early 2023 with cloudy cornea, a finding consistent with lesions described in waterfowl that have survived avian influenza infection. This bird was among those that had antibodies to the virus.

AI virus antibodies against H5 were detected in 24% of the DP adults and immatures captured in early 2023. Two individuals out of those carrying antibodies had cloudy corneas, a finding that is consistent with the lesions described in waterfowl that have survived H5N1 infection. No antibodies were detected in the adult or immature individuals captured in early 2024.

The presence of H5-specific antibodies in 2023 confirms exposure to an H5 subtype AI virus. Together with the cloudy corneas of two of the DPs with antibodies, this may suggest exposure to H5N1 and survival. Since we do not have data on how long antibodies can be detected in the blood of pelicans after infection, this could have happened either during the 2022 outbreak or during the subsequent autumn migration. In either case this would be a very heartening result, as it suggests that DPs can survive H5N1 infection and could develop lasting immunity to infection. However, it should be noted that this finding could also result from the pelicans in question being recently exposed to any H5 subtype AI virus, either low pathogenic or highly pathogenic. In other words, an AI virus that is completely unrelated to the previous outbreak or the globally circulating H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4.b. Nonetheless, should exposure to a different H5 virus have occurred, it could still confer some immunity against a new infection with the highly pathogenic H5N1.

PERSISTENCE OF THE AI VIRUS IN THE ENVIRONMENT

All the nesting material and faecal samples collected in December 2022 tested negative for the AI virus, thus indicating that the virus was no longer circulating in the Prespa colony. These samples were collected as a proactive measure before the onset of the breeding period that followed the outbreak and the findings were encouraging. As there were no signs of the AI virus circulating in Greece in 2023, sampling was not repeated.

OTHER PATHOGENS WEST NILE VIRUS AND OTHER FLAVIVIRUSES

All samples were also tested for West Nile virus (WNV), a mosquito-borne flavivirus transmitted between mosquitos and wild birds, as well as for other flaviviruses, such as Usutu virus, which is known to circulate in Greece. These viruses can infect and cause disease in birds, although often they are not directly disease-causing but instead suppress the immune system, allowing for secondary infections to take hold. The epidemiology of flaviviruses is closely linked to the dynamics of mosquito populations, which vary according to climatic conditions, especially temperature and humidity.

No samples from either DP or GWP Prespa nestlings collected in 2022 tested positive for antibodies against WNV or other flaviviruses. In contrast, 48% of the adult DPs sampled in early 2023 had antibodies against WNV or other flaviviruses, while amongst the nestlings sampled in 2023 significantly more GWPs (31%) than DPs (2.2%) had antibodies. Hence, data on WNV and flavivirus exposure does not suggest that WNV infection is implicated in susceptibility to the AI virus.

Long-term studies on WNV epidemiology have shown that warm winters are related to more intense circulation of the virus. The winter of 2022-2023 was significantly warmer than 2021-2022, at least in Prespa, which could partially explain the differences in the prevalence of the virus between the two sampling years. The higher predominance of WNV in GWPs could be related to the colour of the down of the chicks, which is very dark compared to the white down of DP chicks, as studies have shown that darker colours attract more mosquitoes, because they absorb and trap heat more than lighter colours.

OTHER PATHOGENS BACTERIA IDENTIFIED IN THE CHOANAL CLEFT

As expected from previous studies on respiratory tract bacteria in other species, a considerable diversity of bacteria was detected in the choanal cleft of pelicans. In total 39 different species were found, however the composition of the species detected was surprising. Significantly more bacterial species were found in nestlings than in adults, and DP nestlings harboured a higher number of different species of bacteria in the choanal cleft than GWP nestlings.

Among the bacteria obtained from adults, *Staphylococcus aureus* was the most frequently found, as it was present in 86% of adults sampled. Other staphylococci were also present in low numbers. Other species of bacteria were also detected in lower densities, such as *Enterococcus*, *Streptococcus* and *Butianxella* species, as well as *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*).

In the case of nestlings, *Staphylococcus* was also the most frequent genus occurring in all nestlings. *Enterococcus* was the second most frequent genus, while *E.coli* was also frequently isolated.

The high numbers of *Staphylococcus* found in pelicans cannot easily be explained and should be studied further. Staphylococci frequently colonise the skin and upper respiratory tract of humans and animals and generally exist in commensalism, an association between two organisms in which one benefits and the other derives neither benefit nor harm, though different species can also cause serious infections, especially *Staphylococcus aureus*. However, in comparison to domestic fowl, or other wild birds such as storks or owls, the amount of *Staphylococcus* carried by DPs and GWPs is very high. It is therefore important to understand whether this is a species-specific commensalism or if it

poses any risk to the pelicans. The high numbers of *S. aureus* carried by birds such as storks have been associated with exposure to waste whilst foraging in landfills. Livestock have also been shown to be an important source of staphylococci, particularly domestic pigs. The development of antimicrobial resistance by staphylococci can be a risk for both human and animal health and is frequent in human environments and in livestock production.

OTHER PATHOGENS ENTERIC BACTERIA IDENTIFIED IN THE CLOACA

E. coli prevalence in Dalmatian pelican nestlings sampled at five different colonies in Greece.

Cloacal bacteria composition was highly diverse as would be expected. In total 88 different strains of enteric bacteria were identified from cloacal samples; enteric bacteria are those that typically exist in the intestines of animals and humans.

In adult pelicans, *E. coli* was the most frequent of the enteric bacteria detected. *E. coli* is commonly found in the digestive tract of both animals and humans, where it resides commensally. The next most frequently detected enteric bacteria were from the genus *Enterococcus*.

In nestlings, *E. coli* was detected in two thirds of the samples, and more often in GWP nestlings than in DP nestlings, although the differences were not significant. However, *Enterococcus* was the most frequently identified genus in nestlings.

E. coli prevalence was significantly lower at the Messolonghi and Kerkini colonies than in the Amvrakikos, Karla and Prespa colonies. These differences between colonies could indicate the overall environmental health of the wetlands. For example, Lake Kerkini, which had a low prevalence of *E. coli*, receives large amounts of water from the Strymon River. The continuous renewal of the water probably prevents the establishment of permanent eutrophic conditions, which can increase the occurrence of bacterial pathogens. In contrast, Karla Reservoir, where there was a high prevalence of *E. coli*, suffers from serious eutrophication with frequent cyanobacterial blooms.

ADDITIONAL NOTEWORTHY RESULTS

Antimicrobial resistant bacteria

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) occurs when bacteria, viruses, fungi and parasites change over time and are no longer overcome by medicines, making infections harder to treat and increasing the risk of the spread of disease, severe illness and death. Consequently, AMR is considered to be one of the world's most urgent public health problems. AMR generally develops in relation to the inappropriate use of antibiotics in humans or domestic animals, whether pets or livestock. Wildlife is not normally treated with antibiotics, but animals, especially wild birds, that are adapted to farm environments or to foraging at wastewater treatment plants or on rubbish dumps, can encounter residues of antimicrobial resistant bacteria.

Interestingly, several bacteria from pelican samples showed some degree of AMR. In particular, the finding of an 'Extended Spectrum Beta Lactamase' (ESBL) producing *E.coli* (see the box on the right) suggests that these bacteria may have been acquired as a result of exposure to an anthropogenic point source. Moreover, GWP nestlings showed a higher prevalence of AMR in staphylococci than DP nestlings, which also suggests that they were exposed to some source of resistant bacteria, or antimicrobial residues. This finding raises questions about the potential negative impact on pelicans in general that may result from changes to their intestinal microbiota from exposure to these bacteria.

ENTEROPATHOGENIC *E.coli*: A HIGH-RISK ANTIBIOTIC-RESISTANT CLONE

The detection of an ESBL-producing *E. coli* strain in 3 adult DPs was an especially worrying finding. ESBLs (Extended-spectrum beta-lactamase) are a serious global health problem, as they are resistant to common antibiotics and may require complex treatments, and this particular high-risk strain is recognised as widely spread. Research has shown that ESBL-producing *E. coli* can survive water treatment processes, and that hospital wastewater can contribute to the spread of these bacteria in the aquatic environment.

A number of instances of wild birds harbouring ESBL-producing bacteria have been noted in recent years, including in other pelican species, which puts the spotlight on migratory birds and the role they could play in dispersing these bacteria, due to their ability to connect different ecosystems and remote locations.

This finding therefore requires monitoring and the tracking of possible sources. It is also stressed that DPs may play a crucial role as **sentinels of AMR in the aquatic environment**, as they visit many different wetlands throughout the year. Sentinel species are those which provide a warning of dysfunction, or an imbalance of the environment, and can be used to detect risks to humans. From a conservation point of view, AMR in bacteria can cause severe disease in animals and humans including birds. Thus, increases in AMR could also indicate a higher potential to cause disease in the pelicans that carry these bacteria.

BACTERIOCINS: PELICANS AS POSSIBLE PROVIDERS OF A FUTURE SOLUTION TO STAPHYLOCOCCUS INFECTIONS IN HUMANS

The high prevalence of staphylococci found in pelicans, especially the wide spectrum of bacteriocins detected in these species triggered an additional study on these bacteriocin-producing bacteria. Bacteriocins are inhibiting substances that can constrain other bacteria and are a promising solution to human bacterial infections in the face of AMR emergence. This finding highlights the important contribution of biodiversity to pressing One Health problems such as the increasing appearance of multi-drug-resistant bacteria.

An initiative of the World Health Organisation, One Health is an integrated approach recognising that the health of humans, domestic and wild animals, plants, and ecosystems are closely linked and interdependent. Collaboration across sectors and disciplines contributes to addressing health challenges such as the emergence of infectious diseases, AMR and food safety, to promote the health of our ecosystems and global health security.

WHAT HAVE WE LEARNED FROM ALL THIS?

Highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) has recently spread into wildlife in unprecedented numbers and across diverse species, presenting an existential threat to the world's biodiversity and threatening long-term conservation efforts. The currently evolving situation and steady advance of HPAI worldwide confirm the significance of studies such as this. It is crucial to enhance our understanding of the factors behind the spread and evolution of the AI virus, which will help to inform management decisions that could prevent or mitigate future outbreaks.

Although the study has not provided conclusive answers to all the stated research questions, it did produce a wealth of information on the epidemiology of pathogens in the two pelican species studied and their exposure to the AI virus.

EXPOSURE OF DPs TO THE AI VIRUS

The presence of antibodies against HPAI in 1 out of 4 DP adults captured after the outbreak demonstrates the likely survival of some infected breeders. Despite the high losses at the Lesser Prespa colony, the 2022 breeding season was not a complete failure for the DP. Around 150 nests were established during the late stages of the outbreak and produced young. Whether these were built by late-arriving birds or by birds that survived the outbreak is difficult to say, however, the study indicates that the latter could be possible.

Since no viral genetic material from DPs and/or GWPs infected by the AI virus in 2022 was available, there was limited capacity for comparative analysis of the outbreak strain and other H5N1 strains that were circulating throughout Europe and Asia at the time. However, during the final stages of this research, several sequences became available on the central AI sequence database, GISAID, and a comprehensive global analysis of European AI virus sequences including the ones in Greek pelicans, showed an intense spread and transmission from North Central and Northwestern Europe to South Central Europe and across Southern Europe, including Greece.

Information received by the team regarding a large outbreak of HPAI, H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b, in DPs in the Urals and Western Siberia in 2021, raises the question of a possible relation with the 2022 outbreak in Prespa. Although populations from the two regions are not directly connected, according to existing knowledge, other species, such as the Eurasian wigeon (*Mareca penelope*, a duck species) and/or other ducks, may connect the two regions. Investigations of recent seabird outbreaks suggest that a single virus introduction event can spread rapidly and lead to a devastating outbreak. These studies also show

that such outbreaks trigger long-distance movements of surviving birds that could contribute to long-distance spread.

Consequently, neither of the two initial scenarios regarding the exposure of breeding Prespa DPs can be confirmed. Although we cannot exclude the possibility that pelicans acquired the AI virus at their wintering or staging grounds through contact with infected surviving DPs or other waterbirds, this scenario looks weak. It is known that DPs do not travel directly to the Lesser Prespa colony from their wintering grounds, as telemetry data has documented the use of various stopover sites, where DPs spend several days to weeks before they finally reach their final destination at Prespa. In addition, Lesser Prespa was the first wetland in Greece to record mass DP deaths, on February 17th. The timing of mass deaths in wetlands en route to Lesser Prespa was more than 2 weeks later, on March 8th at Lake Kerkini. Lastly, the incubation period for H5N1 ranges from 2 to 5 days on average and up to 17 days (source: World Health Organisation). Taking these factors into consideration, the scenario of an infected DP arriving at the Lesser Prespa colony and spreading the disease seems unlikely.

The more probable scenario appears to be that pelicans were contaminated at their breeding grounds through contact with the secretions of other, infected but asymptomatic, species. Interestingly, just before the onset of the outbreak, the annual International Waterbird Census, in mid-January 2022, recorded, in Lesser Prespa Lake, a three-fold increase in wintering waterbird numbers compared to the average of previous years. Many wintering waterbirds at Prespa use pelican nesting islets as roosting and resting sites. At this time of year, most pelicans have not yet arrived, so ducks, geese, swans and other birds make ample use of these safe havens and the faeces they leave behind could have resulted in subsequent pelican contamination with the AI virus.

PERSISTENCE OF THE AI VIRUS IN PELICANS AND THE ENVIRONMENT

Data collected in this study seem to preclude the persistence of the AI virus in the long term, as none of the seropositive DPs was shedding the virus. This is consistent with the findings of a griffon vulture study in Spain, in which nestlings were not shedding, despite high AI virus antibody levels in their blood. Furthermore, no signs of the persistence of the AI virus in the environment (waterbird faeces mainly sampled) were detected eight months after the end of the outbreak. Yet, the persistence of the virus in the water is still uncertain and investigated.

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF DP COLONIES AND DP/GWP IN REGARD TO SUSCEPTIBILITY TO THE AI VIRUS

None of the results provided clear evidence for associated diseases that could explain the higher susceptibility of DPs to H5N1 in comparison to GWPs. The choanal microbiota appears to be more diverse in DP nestlings than in GWP nestlings, while differences in the prevalences of cloacal bacteria between GWPs and DPs were limited to specific species. In fact, a more diverse microbiota appears to be more effective in both controlling and preventing infection with HPAI, as has been shown in mallards. While the study found significant differences between colonies in some important bacteria, such as *E. coli*, these do not explain the susceptibility of Prespa DPs to the AI virus. In the two Greek coastal colonies, the absence of DP deaths during the 2022 outbreak could be attributed to the biochemistry and location of these wetlands. In general, the viability of the AI virus in natural waters decreases with increasing salinity and infectivity is potentially greatest in cooler, freshwater habitats.

The exposure of pelicans to AMR bacteria is an overall worrying finding and further investigation would increase understanding of potential health effects. Pelicans primarily use freshwater wetlands, where several AMR bacteria have been found in Greece. AMR bacteria reach rivers and lakes through discharges from wastewater treatment plants, as well as leaching from nearby farms. Livestock are also an important pathway and are considered a significant reservoir of life-threatening enterobacteria (ESBLs). Leached contaminants from farms near wetlands or lakes can end up in water. Moreover, cattle often come to lakes to graze and drink and could thus contribute to the contamination of the aquatic environment. It is worth mentioning that extensive cattle grazing takes place on the shoreline, or even inside the wetlands, around the eastern DP colonies investigated in this study, namely Lake Kerkini, Lesser Prespa Lake and Karla Reservoir.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Dr Panagiotis Azmanis, a veterinary specialist in Zoological Medicine (Avian), who contributed to the conception and design of the study. Special thanks to Julia Henderson who improved the English of the article and provided useful comments that improved text clarity and Teresa Cardona-Cabrera and Sara Minayo who participated in the laboratory analysis and provided the figures and photos from the lab.

Proposed citation:

Alexandrou, O., Catsadorakis, G. & U. Höfle. 2025. Ecoepidemiology of avian influenza and other diseases in Dalmatian pelicans – Summary Brief. Society for the Protection of Prespa, Greece/SaBio Health and Biotechnology Department, Institute for Game and Wildlife Research (UCLM-CSIC-JCCM), Spain. 36 pp.

Photographic material:

©SPP Archive / G. Catsadorakis (p.3, 22)

©SPP Archive (p.8, p.10-11)

©SPP Archive / O. Alexandrou (p.16, 19)

©SPP Archive / T. Cardona-Cabrera (p.17)

©SPP Archive / L. Nikolaou (p.15)

©SPP Archive / Francisco Márquez/ The Living Med (p.6, 20, 31, 33)

Envato Elements: License Code Z83FXD47G9 (Cover)

Graphic Design:

Productive Land - www.p-l.gr

